

THE ROLE OF NATIONAL-CULTURAL TRADITIONS AND INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF ETHNO TOURISM

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Abstract. *Ethno tourism better-known type of tourism, cultural tourism-is one of the fastest-developing industries in tourism where the cultural and ethnic features of different peoples are explored. This article looks at how national-cultural traditions and intangible cultural heritage have influenced the development of ethno tourism. The research dwells on traditions, rituals, folklore, and crafts that are considered to be the core aspects of intangible cultural heritage in the context of their significance for tourist traffic. It is concluded that preservation and promotion of cultural values increase tourist flows, strengthen ethnic identity, and social cohesion.*

Keywords: *ethno tourism, national-cultural traditions, intangible cultural heritage, cultural tourism, preservation of cultural heritage, ethnic identity.*

Introduction

Ethno tourism is a type of tourism that has a specific purpose: it is aimed at the familiarization of tourists with the traditions, customs, and cultures of different ethnic groups. Ethno tourism may be the critical means for preserving and popularizing intangible cultural heritage in globalization and urbanization processes when most of the traditional cultural practices are under the threat of disappearing. It is the national-cultural traditions-folk dances, music, cuisine, rituals, and crafts-that constitute the very ground for the development of specific tourist products attractive for travelers from all over the world.

The national-cultural traditions mean all varieties of cultural activities passed from one generation to another. They reflect the distinctive and unique features of ethnic groups and represent an integral part of their cultural identity. In ethno tourism, these traditions serve as a ground for developing the corresponding attractive tourist routes and programs. For instance, traditional ceremonies, ethnic festivals, and local customs enable tourists to engage more meaningfully with the cultural history of different peoples and to participate in genuinely cultural events.

Intangible cultural heritage covers oral traditions and expressions, performing arts, social customs, rituals, and festivals but also traditional knowledge and skills. This type of heritage underlines cultural diversity and the richness of human activity, being a resource in the establishment of ethno tourism. In this respect, craft workshops, gastronomic tours, classes of traditional artistic expression, and participation in local ceremonies and festivals also allow tourists to become not only observers but also active actors in the cultural life of the communities.

The successful development of ethno-tourism requires the establishment of favorable conditions: not only infrastructure and logistics but also personnel who could represent the cultural heritage of the region. In this respect, one should point out that commercialization of cultural traditions can lead to grave consequences, namely their distortion and loss of authenticity. In this respect, ethical standards and principles of sustainable tourism have to be worked out. In particular,

tourism activities based on the collaboration with local communities respect the culture and traditions of an indigenous people. These all are vital aspects of sustainable ethno tourism development.

While there are a lot of benefits to ethno tourism, there are also quite a few challenges that accompany the practice. Of the concerns, commodification is the principal, which suggests cultural practices change or are simplified in order to make them more acceptable to tourists and make them less authentic. This could be overwhelming for local communities and disturb long-standing ways of life. With sustainable management, though, ethno tourism has the potential to bring in economic benefits to the locals, foster cultural exchange, and drive interest in preserving at-risk cultural traditions.

Ethno tourism opportunities of Rishton, Chust and Boysun districts

Rishton is a city in the Fergana Valley, famous for its rich pottery traditions, dating back more than 800 years. Local clay and famous "ishkor" glaze give this town's unique ceramics their peculiar blue and green hues. Here, traditional workshops of potters allow one to see the work of master ceramists and try creating and painting pottery with one's hands. One must draw special attention to the Ceramics Museum of Rustam Usmanov, which presents history and technics of Rishtan ceramics. And local bazaars in Rishton, being the initial point, can provide all decently made pottery, with every single piece reflecting artistic heritage. Engage with the native families and artists for an intimate experience about their crafts and customs, truly immersive.

The very city of **Chust**, in the Namangan region, allows for a visit to the local craftsmanship of knifemaking. Across the whole Central Asian region, so-called "knife", or Chust knives, are famous for their solidity and complicating design. Workers of the local workshops teach how to forge, give shape, and decorate this kind of knife according to traditional techniques; sometimes, the master artisans invite visitors to watch or try a little bit themselves. The Chust Knife Museum is a small but insightful place in which one can learn about the history and cultural meaning of this craft. There are also beautifully embroidered skullcaps-or doppis-found by him in Chust, symbols of Uzbek identity. The local artisans use intricate patterns passed down from generation to generation, and visitors are allowed to witness how embroidery is done and buy these unique items directly from the craftsmen. The vivid markets here are full of traditional crafts and textiles, which makes them very good for experiencing local culture and artistry.

Boysun is a region in the area of Surkhandarya and is famous for its cultural treasure trove, which has been recognized by UNESCO due to its unique folklore and traditions. The Boysun Bahori Festival is one of the year's highlights regarding cultural expression with its traditional music, dances, and handcrafts. The heritage of the region, from ancient rituals to folk performances to traditional dress, would be vividly represented during the festival. Boysun's mountain villages, one example being Kisht, allowed one to experience rural life unchanged for centuries, with customs maintained and performed just as they always had been. The visitors could participate in traditions like bread baking and embroidery and receive hospitality from the villagers. The region is also widely famous for its typical suzani and carpets, made in full accordance with traditional weaving methods. Boysun music and dance, with traditional instruments like doira and dutar, are part of the boysun cultural experience, which corresponds to deep-rooted traditions of this particular area.

Conclusion

The development of ethno tourism in Uzbekistan, particularly in regions like Rishton, Chust, and Boysun, highlights the country's rich cultural heritage and diverse traditions. These

areas offer unique experiences through their renowned crafts, such as Rishtan's ceramics, Chust's knifemaking and embroidery, and Boysun's traditional music and folklore. Ethno tourism not only promotes cultural preservation but also enhances economic opportunities for local communities, fostering cultural exchange and strengthening social cohesion. However, sustainable management and ethical standards are crucial to prevent the commodification of cultural traditions and to ensure the authenticity and integrity of these practices. By supporting and promoting the intangible cultural heritage of these regions, ethno tourism can serve as a powerful tool for preserving and celebrating Uzbekistan's unique cultural identity.

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